

Landscape typology analysis in Slovenia through image analytics

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Abstract. Classifying landscapes into types is challenging because they are continuous, but it is essential for effective protection, management, and planning, as similar processes of change occur within the same landscape types. This study aimed to classify landscape types through image analytics. Landscape photographs were embedded using the Inception v3 model within the visual programming toolbox Orange. The best classification performance was achieved with logistic regression, with an area under the curve (AUC) of 0,995 and a classification accuracy of 0,930. The second-best method was k-nearest neighbors (AUC = 0,947), while the classification tree performed the worst (AUC = 0,820). Hierarchical clustering and t-SNE results were unsatisfactory, despite the selected photographs being representative and landscape typology being simplified into five types.

Submission Type. Analysis, case study.

BoK Concepts. [AM5] Basic analytical methods, [IP3] Image understanding

Keywords. landscape typology, classification, image analytics, Slovenia

1 Introduction

Complex systems are better understood when categorized. Within the same landscape types, comparable processes of change occur, allowing for the definition of similar conservation and development objectives. This study aimed to categorize landscape photographs into landscape types, to facilitate effective protection, management, and planning, as mandated by the European Landscape Convention.

2 Data and Methods

100 images were selected from the photography database of the renovation of the landscape regionalization in Slovenia (Golobič et al., 2024). They were manually categorized into five broad landscape types: wooded, high-production agricultural, mosaic agricultural, watery, and meadow landscapes. Each type included 20 images.

For analysis, the visual programming toolbox Orange 3.39.0 (Demšar et al., 2013) was utilized. The images were embedded using the Inception v3 model (Szegedy et al., 2015). Hierarchical clustering using cosine distance and the Ward method produced a dendrogram, which was further examined with the Distributions widget. Next, a stratified 10-fold cross-validation evaluated the accuracy of classification methods: logistic regression, classification tree, and k-nearest neighbors (kNN). Errors were analyzed with the Confusion Matrix, and data were visualized in a 2D with t-distributed stochastic neighbour embedding (t-SNE). Misclassified images were further analyzed by examining their nearest neighbors. Finally, the images' geographical locations were mapped using ArcGIS Pro 3.6.1. For 28 photographs, location data was missing, so the centroid of the corresponding landscape subunit was assigned.

2.1 Data and Software Availability Section

Data supporting this publication are accessible and available in the national spatial information system's digital database (Golobič et al., 2025). A list of selected photographs is in Appendix 1.

The analysis was executed using Orange (Demšar et al., 2013), available under the GNU General Public License on GitHub (Bioinformatics Laboratory, 2026).

Figure 1. Dendrogram created in Orange (Demšar et al., 2013) using hierarchical clustering with cosine distances and Ward aggregation method.

The visualisation of the photographs' location was done in ArcGIS Pro version 3.6.1., which is not available due to licensing restrictions.

3 Results and discussion

Cluster evaluation showed that the created clusters are meaningful, but their quality varies as shown in Fig. 1. The highest-quality cluster included all images depicting high-production agricultural landscapes, along with three images of other types. Logistic regression performed best in image classification achieving an area under the curve (AUC) of 0,995. KNN was second (AUC = 0,947); the classification tree was worst (AUC = 0,820). This may be because Inception v3 (Szegedy et al., 2015) is a convolutional neural network and therefore consists of logistic regressions. Using logistic regression, 7 images were misclassified (see Fig. 2). Most errors involved images that were somewhat misleading, such as a meadow landscape with a forest patch, which was misclassified as wooded. The t-SNE plot showed that high-production agricultural and watery landscapes formed clearly distinct groups (the latter with two exceptions). Wooded, mosaic agricultural, and meadow landscapes created some one-landscape-type areas, but they were also mixed at the borders. This may be due to mixed content in images, with parts showing different landscape types from those labelled, resembling complex,

transitional landscapes. Reviewing misclassified images' nearest neighbors confirmed this.

A limitation is simplifying landscape typology into five types, while experts recognized 31 (Golobič et al., 2024). Another is the small, manually selected photograph sample, which could introduce bias.

4 Conclusion

Mapping landscape types is challenging because they are continuous. Although classification was successful, hierarchical clustering and t-SNE results were unsatisfactory, even with representative photos and a simplified landscape typology of five types. Future research could include more landscape types and larger photo samples. Developing this further may enable mapping landscape types with social media photos, enhancing monitoring, coordination, unified measures, and supporting better planning, conservation, and management based on landscape types.

Declaration of Generative AI in writing

The author states I used Generative AI for language editing only, with Grammarly enhancing grammar and structure.

Figure 2. Locations of photographs, colored by landscape type and classification accuracy of logistic regression.

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Szegedy, C., Vanhoucke, V., Ioffe, S., Shlens, J., and Wojna, Z.: Rethinking the Inception Architecture for Computer Vision, <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1512.00567>, 11 December 2015.

Appendix 1: List of selected photographs from the database (Golobič et al., 2024)

1.1.1.04 krma z debele peči.jpg	2_3_3_08_Menina_Biba_planina_pašnik_suhozid_skale_J_X.jpg
1.1.2.01_1_Perniki_jasa.JPG	2_3_4_04_Tihaboj_BK.jpg
1.1.2.01_6_mežakla_gozdnate_planote.JPG	22302_01_Sava_Zbilje_N.JPG
1.1.2.02_2_pokljuka_gozdnate_planote.jpg	22302_02_Hraše_N.JPG
1.1.2.02_IK_uskovnica_1.jpg	22403_01_Selo_pri_Vodicah.JPG
1.1.2.02_IK_uskovnica_3.jpg	22405_02_Brinje_daljnovod_N.JPG
1.1.2.03_IK_Bohinj_jezero.jpg	23404_04_Brunk_N.JPG
1.1.3.02_krnski_hribi.JPG	3.3.2.01_05_pritisk - Na robovih Šentjerneja_TA.JPG
1.1.3.02_pod_bogatinom.JPG	3.3.2.03_02_vodna_in_obvodna_krajina_z_akumulacijskim_jezerom_HE_Brežice_TA.JPG
1.1.4.01_korita_soc_e_mg.jpg	3_2_4_03_Šmarje_iz_sv_Roka_BK.jpg
1.2.2.01_planinica_nad_Drago.JPG	3_3_3_01_Trška_gora_JH.jpg
1.3.1.04_cojzova_1.jpg	3_3_4_Otočec_otoki_v_Krki.JPG
1.3.1.07_pogled_s_kamniskega_vrha_1.jpg	31101_03_Ledavsko_jezero.JPG
1.3.2.07_Golte_pogled_z_Menine_2_J - Copy (2).jpg	31101_04_mozaične_kmetijske_ravnine_Sotina_PTO.JPG
1_3_1_06_Velika_planina_Kapela_Marije_Snežne_PTO_J_X.jpg	31102_02_ravninske_njivske_krajine_Prosejnakovci.JPG
1_3_1_06_Velika_planina_vrtače_posamične_smreke_J_X.jpg	31102_04_Izjemna_Kobilje.JPG
1_3_2_02_Savinja_Robanov_kot_regulirana_J_X.jpg	31201_01_izjemna_Lendavske_Gorice_PTO.JPG
1_3_2_05_Lučnica_Podveža_J_X.jpg	31301_01_ravninske_njivske_krajine_Dokležovje.JPG
1_3_2_06_Pogled_z_Menine_na_V_del_celki_PTO_J.jpg	31301_03_zaplate_gozda_s_Suhega_Vrha.JPG
2.1.4.01_selska_sora_vodne_ureditve.JPG	31302_02_ravninske_njivske_krajine_bližu_Lendave.JPG
2.1.4.05_pogled_z_Vrha_sv_treh_kraljev_na_zirovsko_gozdnata_slemena.....JPG	31303_04_ojezerjena_gramoznica.JPG
2.1.4.07_jamnik_IK_1.JPG	32101_01_Apaško_polje_PTO.JPG
2.1.4.07_gozdnato_hribovje.JPG	32102_01_Ravninska_njivska_krajina_Mota.JPG
2.1.5.02_01_Črni_vrh_izjemna_N.JPG	32102_03_zaplate_gozda_Krapje.JPG
2.1.5.03_04_Koreno_izjemna_N.JPG	32102_04_omejki_skupine_dreves_in_grmovnic_Hrastje.JPG
2.1.5.03_Horjul_PTO.JPG	32203_03_gozdnata_gričevja_Senčak.JPG
2.2.1.01_bled_jezero.JPG	32206_01_mozaična_kmetijska_krajina_na_gričevju_Ži_karce_PTO.JPG
2.2.1.02_mozaicne_ravninske.JPG	32301_01_ravninske_njivske_krajine_infrsrukturni_ko_ridorji.JPG
2.3.2.05_Šmartno_ob_Paki_proti_jugu_BK.jpg	4_4_2_01_Laze_nad_Krko_J_X.jpg
2.3.2.06_Šmartinsko_jezero_BK.jpg	4_4_3_02_Muljavsko_polje_J_X.jpg
2.3.2.06_Žalec_hmeljišča_BK.jpg	4_4_3_02_Šentpavelsko_polje_J_X.jpg
2.3.5.02_Laško_BK.jpg	4_4_3_03_Dvorska_gora_vinogradi_PTO_J_X.jpg

4_4_3_04_Mali_Vrh_PTO_J_X.jpg
4_4_3_06_Trebča_vas_J_X.JPG
4_5_1_02_Kavce_Gabrje_J_X.jpg
4_5_2_01_Jerneja_vas_J_X.JPG
4_5_2_03_Kolpa_pri_Vinici_J_X.JPG
41104_1_Grgar_kraško polje_N.JPG
41301_02_Nanos_N.JPG
42404_04_Turjak_N.JPG
425_07_nad Ilirsko Bistrico_N.JPG
512_Kanal.JPG
52101_511_Z Vrhovelj p K proti Koradi.JPG
52102_dolina Birše.JPG
52102_z Višnjevika na Vedrijan.JPG
522_HE Solkan.JPG
52302_01_Pobočja Trnovske planote med Kamnjami in Stomažem_PTO_K.JPG
52304_06_Branik_PTO_K.JPG
52402_Sveto pri Komnu_izjemna.JPG
52602_05_Dragonja_KB.JPG
53101_Vremščica.jpg
53301_Slavnik 2.jpg
53301_Slavnik1.jpg
Drava med Loko in Vurberkom.JPG
Dravsko polje_Kidričevo s Ptujске Gore.JPG
IMG_2255.JPG
IMG_2445.JPG
IMG_2696.JPG
Kubed01.jpg
Kubed02.jpg
Neverke_tovarna krmil.JPG
Otllica gmajna.JPG
Otllica pokopališče.JPG
Otllica razgledišče.JPG
Pobočja Trnovskega gozda.JPG
Poplavno območje ob Dravi_Ormoške lagune.JPG
Ptujsko polje _daljnovid.JPG
Zreško_konjiške gorice_Polene proti Konjicam.JPG